

GENDER EQUALITY AS A KEY FACTOR IN ENHANCING THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN SOCIETY

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Tashkent Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin

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Аннотация. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda gender tengligini ta'minlash, ayollarning siyosiy, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy hayotdagi ishtirokini kengaytirish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan islohotlar tahlil qilinadi. Ayollarni qo'llab-quvvatlashga qaratilgan davlat dasturlari, ta'lim imkoniyatlari, tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, ularni tazyiq va zo'ravonlikdan himoya qilishga oid normativ-huquqiy asoslar keng yoritiladi. Mazkur maqolada I.M. Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti Toshkent filiali misolida ayollar faolligini oshirishning amaliy mexanizmlari ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Калит so'zlar: gender tenglik, ayollar huquqlari, ijtimoiy siyosat, ta'lim, tadbirkorlik, ayollarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, zo'ravonlikning oldini olish.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы обеспечения гендерного равенства и расширения участия женщин в политической, социальной и экономической жизни Республики Узбекистан. Освещаются государственные программы по поддержке женщин, предоставление образовательных возможностей, развитие женского предпринимательства, а также меры по защите женщин от притеснения и насилия. Отдельное внимание уделено практическому опыту Филиала РГУ нефти и газа имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте в повышении активности девушек и создании условий для реализации их потенциала.

Ключевые слова: гендерное равенство, права женщин, социальная политика, образование, женское предпринимательство, поддержка женщин, предотвращение насилия.

Abstract. This article examines key issues related to ensuring gender equality and expanding the participation of women in the political, social, and economic spheres of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It highlights state programs aimed at supporting women, increasing access to education, promoting women's entrepreneurship, and strengthening legal protections against harassment and violence. The paper also presents practical mechanisms for enhancing women's engagement based on the experience of the Tashkent Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin.

Keywords: gender equality, women's rights, social policy, education, women's entrepreneurship, women's support, prevention of violence.

Today, women take an active part in public administration, make key political decisions, develop social initiatives, and implement major business projects. History shows that caring mothers, wives, and daughters have played significant roles in shaping many great personalities. In this regard, ensuring women's rights and interests, achieving gender equality, and protecting the family, motherhood, and childhood have become priorities of state policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Comprehensive measures are being taken to provide girls and women with opportunities to engage in business and entrepreneurship, develop farming enterprises, and

implement advanced scientific and innovative projects. Jobs are being created for women, and their living and working conditions are steadily improving.

In our country, practical efforts to provide financial support for women’s education and professional growth have already begun and are successfully continuing. The fourth priority area of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022–2026, which focuses on fair social policy and human capital development, outlines measures to expand opportunities for women. Objective 60 of the Strategy defines steps to improve the system of providing high-tech medical care to women, while Objective 69 specifies measures to support women, ensure their active participation in social life, continue gender equality policies, and enhance women’s socio-political engagement. These efforts include promoting women’s education, professional training, employment, entrepreneurship, talent identification, and access to quality medical and social services, particularly in rural areas, as well as fostering healthy lifestyles among women.

It should be noted that in recent years, Uzbekistan has established a solid legal framework for protecting women’s rights and freedoms, including special benefits for university admission and entrepreneurial activity. Furthermore, under the Presidential Decree “On Measures to Further Accelerate Systemic Support for Families and Women”, since the 2022–2023 academic year, the following initiatives have been introduced to create favorable conditions for women’s education and support their scientific and professional development:

- Allocation of at least 1.8 trillion soums annually from the State Budget to commercial banks for seven-year interest-free education loans to women studying at universities, technical schools, and colleges, including evening and correspondence programs;
- Allocation of at least 200 billion soums annually from the State Budget to fully finance the tuition contracts of women enrolled in master’s programs at state higher education institutions;
- Provision of additional scholarships through the “El-Yurt Umidi” Foundation for 50 women to study undergraduate programs and 10 women to pursue master’s degrees abroad each year;
- Full financing of tuition contracts for 150 women annually (a total of 2,100 students) from low-income families, orphans, or those without parental care, through local budget resources;
- Allocation of at least 300 doctoral study quotas annually for women in state scientific organizations and higher education institutions.

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 15, 2022, “On Measures to Pay Tuition Fees for Women Studying in Master’s Programs at State Higher Educational Institutions,” also became a powerful incentive for women to pursue graduate education. Under this resolution, women receive interest-free loans to cover their tuition fees, and extensive outreach activities have been conducted to promote this initiative.

Systematic work is also being carried out to raise women’s participation in all spheres of economic, political, and public life to a new qualitative level, providing comprehensive support for education, professional development, employment, and entrepreneurial initiatives. In particular, the Presidential Decree of March 5, 2021, No. PP-5020 “On Measures to Further Improve the System of Support for Women and Ensure Their Active Participation in Public Life” enables women to receive loans of up to 33 million soums for a period of three years, including a six-month grace period, at an annual rate of 14 percent to start their own businesses.

Legal guarantees for women’s labor rights have also been strengthened. The Presidential Decree “On Measures to Further Strengthen Labor Rights Guarantees and Support Women’s Entrepreneurship” prohibits the termination of open-ended employment contracts at the employer’s initiative due to a woman reaching retirement age or obtaining pension rights before the age of 60, as well as the termination of fixed-term contracts before their expiration.

In 2020, Uzbekistan introduced “Women’s Notebooks” (Ayollar daftari) as an effective instrument of social protection. Through this system, about one million women have received social, economic, medical, legal, and psychological assistance. Measures have also been taken to organize entrepreneurship courses and provide preferential loans for women included in these registers.

In the New Uzbekistan, a climate of intolerance toward harassment and violence against women is being created, ensuring that gender-based discrimination is unacceptable. Violence against women is a major obstacle to achieving progress in equality, development, and peace, as well as in safeguarding women’s rights. This aligns with the core principle of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—to leave no one behind—which cannot be achieved without eradicating violence against women.

At the Tashkent Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin, the Advisory Council on Women’s Issues actively works to strengthen the role of women and girls, protecting their rights and freedoms and providing equal opportunities.

The branch administration, together with the Advisory Council and tutors, regularly monitors the living conditions of female students residing in student housing. Meetings with students focus on maintaining cleanliness and order in common areas to ensure a comfortable and safe living environment. Students also have the opportunity to voice their suggestions for improving living conditions, including infrastructure development and household amenities—showing their strong engagement and readiness for constructive collaboration with the administration.

Female activists of the branch actively participate not only in university life but also in national events. For instance, under the leadership of the Advisory Council Chair, active members of the “Kizlarjon” Club, M. Abdugaffarova and M. Akhmadzhanova, represented the branch at the Republican Forum “Girls – the Support of the Nation” held at the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation. They discussed pressing issues such as girls’ access to education, opportunities for scientific and creative self-realization, and legal protection against discrimination.

Much attention is also paid to promoting a healthy lifestyle and raising a physically active generation. With the support of Uzbekneftegaz JSC, a chess tournament called “Chess Days” was held with the participation of female students from the branch. The participants demonstrated strong strategic thinking and competitive spirit, securing prize-winning places and confirming their dedication and love for this intellectual sport.

A meeting was also organized with Svetlana Valeryevna Osipova, world champion and silver medalist of the Paris 2024 Olympic Games in Taekwondo, who inspired the students with her personal story of perseverance and success.

Women and girls at the branch also actively engage in scientific and educational events. On October 12, 2024, in honor of the International Day of Rural Women (October 15), a roundtable titled “*The Role of Rural Women in Achieving Sustainable Economic Growth and*

Ensuring National Well-being” was held. Participants presented reports on empowering rural women, their achievements in agriculture, science, and education, and the importance of developing leadership, argumentation, and conflict-resolution skills. A comparative analysis of the role of rural women in Uzbekistan and other developed and developing countries generated particular interest.

The branch also regularly holds the traditional “Khan-Atlas” Festival, which promotes Uzbekistan’s rich cultural heritage through traditional clothing. Every Friday, all female teachers, staff, and students wear national attire made of khan-atlas and adras, symbolizing respect for national traditions. These fabrics, with deep historical roots, continue to gain popularity both in Uzbekistan and internationally in the modern fashion industry.

Given that Uzbekistan pays great attention to combating oppression and violence in society, the “Uzbekistan–2030” Strategy emphasizes the creation of a culture of intolerance toward harassment and violence against women and ensuring women’s rights and legitimate interests. The National Human Rights Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with several legislative acts, has established a robust legal foundation for this purpose.

The Law “On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence”, adopted by the Legislative Chamber on August 17, 2019, and approved by the Senate on August 23, 2019, regulates relations in the field of protecting women from all forms of harassment and violence. Based on this law, numerous regulatory and interdepartmental acts have been adopted.

In line with these efforts, the Tashkent Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin developed an internal Policy on the Prevention of Harassment and Violence to ensure a friendly, safe, and healthy working environment and to protect employees from all forms of abuse and discrimination.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that today the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan attaches great importance to strengthening the role of women working in all sectors of the country. It is hoped that these opportunities will further stimulate women’s active participation in public life and contribute significantly to the nation’s development.

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